

Building a semantic-based decision support system to optimize the energy use in public buildings: the OPTIMUS project

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Abstract

The reduction of carbon emissions in cities is a systemic problem, which involves multiple scales and domains and the collaboration of experts from various fields. The “smart city” approach can contribute to improving the energy efficiency of urban areas provided that there is reliable data –from the different domains concerned with carbon emission reduction– to assess their energy performance and to make decisions to improve it. In the SEMANCO project, we applied Semantic Web technologies to solve the interoperability among data, systems, tools, and users in cases dealing with carbon emission reduction in urban areas. In the OPTIMUS project, the tools and methods developed in SEMANCO are being further enhanced and applied to the development of a decision support system (DSS) to help local administrations to optimize the energy use of public buildings.

Keywords

Energy efficiency, decision support systems, smart cities, semantic web, semantic interoperability, energy data models.

Introduction

The “smart city” approach can help to improve the citizens’ quality of life in accordance with the objectives set by sustainable energy policies of the European Union with the target of reducing by 20% the CO₂ emissions by 2020. Smart cities rely on the availability of data. Although there is an increasingly amount of energy and other related data sets available, it is necessary to integrate them in order to provide the various stakeholders involved in the planning of energy efficient cities with the information they need to make well-informed decisions. In fact, the problem of carbon emission reduction in urban areas cannot be constrained to a particular geographical area or scale, or circumscribed to a particular discipline or expert: it is a systemic problem which involves multiple scales and domains and the collaboration of experts from various fields. In addition, having access to the data is not enough.

It is necessary to integrate data from different domains in order to understand the interrelationships between the various areas –energy, economics, health– that are involved in the reduction of carbon emissions in cities.

The application of Semantic Web technologies can help to overcome some of the difficulties which are intrinsic to the development of decision support systems (DSS), in particular those concerning the accessibility to the data and the integration of data from multiple domains. These technologies can be applied, mainly, to support data integration processes and to overcome the interoperability barriers between the data generated by the different users and by the applications in various domains. Currently, efforts are being made to deal with this problem in different areas related to smart cities. For example, the QuerioCity platform relies on Linked Data technologies to manage heterogeneous information stemming from different domains and formats (Lopez *et al.*, 2012). Another example is STAR-CITY, a system to aggregate heterogeneous real-time data with the purpose of exploring, analysing, and predicting traffic conditions in cities (Lécué *et al.*, 2014). Semantic-based interoperability approaches based on ontologies are an alternative to centralized standard data models whose limitations have already been pinpointed: difficulties to reach a consensus among a community of users; lack of flexibility of the data models to adapt to changes; and loss of information after exporting and importing data through applications (Sicilia *et al.*, 2014). Nevertheless, data interoperability is not only a technological challenge: it also involves devising and applying procedures to avoid doing redundant work, to reduce design errors, and to be replicable in other contexts. Therefore, the technological solutions need to be embedded in scenarios which encompass strategic goals, users and systems, along with the tools to analyse the data and mechanisms of data provision and data cleansing.

This paper contains a report on the development of a semantic-based Decision Support System (DSS) to optimize energy use in public buildings, which is being carried out by OPTIMUS project co-funded by the 7th Framework Programme. The goal of the OPTIMUS DSS is to suggest short-term decisions to optimize the energy performance of buildings based on the analysis of five types of data distributed by heterogeneous and dynamic sources: weather conditions, social behaviour, building energy performance, energy prices, and renewable energy production.

The work on semantic data modelling carried out in the OPTIMUS project is based on the results obtained in a previous project SEMANCO, carried out with the support of 7th Framework Programme from 2011 to 2015. These results refer to the procedures to design an ontology as well as to specific outcomes which are applied to the OPTIMUS project, such as the SEMANCO ontology and the ontology editing tools which were developed in this last project. With regard to the data being semantically integrated, the main difference between the two projects- SEMANCO and OPTIMUS- is that the first is focused mainly on static data needed to make middle to long-term planning decisions, while in the second one we are dealing mostly with dynamic data and short-term decisions making processes.

SEMANCO: the process to create a semantic-based platform to support decision making

The goal of the SEMANCO project was to create a semantic-based integrated platform to support the planning of energy efficient urban areas, with the participation of the different stakeholders involved: planners, policy makers and energy consultants. The reasons to use semantic technologies in this project were twofold: 1. From an instrumental point of view, these technologies enable the integration of distributed and heterogeneous data and 2. From a conceptual perspective, the process of designing an ontology enables groups of experts to jointly define the problem to be solved in terms of concepts and relationships between them. Therefore, in SEMANCO, the knowledge that a group of experts (energy consultants, planners, policy makers) had about energy efficiency planning in urban areas was formalised as an ontology created with the participation of the domain experts and the ontology engineers. Data needed to model the problem and to propose solution scenarios was integrated using semantic technologies.

Experts' knowledge is bound to the tools and methods in their particular disciplines, it is shaped by their experience, and it is constrained by the information they have at their disposal. To make this knowledge explicit, so that it can be formalised as an ontology, use cases were defined for each of the pilot cities participating in the SEMANCO project. A use case stands for a simplified model of a complex reality constructed with three components and their interrelationships: the data available to model the problem, the tools used to process the data and the experts who use the data and tools to model a problem and find the solutions to it (Madrazo *et al.*, 2013).

An ontology developed from the information captured through use cases stands for a formal representation of the knowledge that experts had with regard to the problem modelled through the use case. The ontology was developed in two stages: 1. Creation of an informal vocabulary to describe the problem at stake including the definition of terms, the data categories and relations between them which was structured in the Energy Standard Tables. These tables provided a link between the knowledge that experts had about a particular problem of energy efficiency and the information available (Corrado *et al.*, 2015)–, and 2. Creation of a formal specification of the terms and relations using standard languages of the Semantic Web such as Web Ontology Language (OWL). This was done by means of Click-On⁶, an ontology editor developed within the project (Wolters *et al.*, 2013).

The methods and tools developed in SEMANCO project are generic enough to be used in other domains. Planning energy efficiency buildings in an urban context is the domain of the SEMANCO ontology. However, this domain can be extended to include the energy performance of buildings in-use, as we have done in the OPTIMUS project.

⁶ <http://www.semanco-tools.eu/click-on>

The development of the OPTIMUS DSS

The goal of the OPTIMUS project is to help local authorities to optimise the energy performance of public buildings by applying the measures suggested by a Decision Support System (DSS), which handles data obtained from a diversity of sources and domains. The application scenarios upon which the SEMANCO platform was built were aimed at supporting long-term decisions (e.g. urban planning) and were mostly based on the use of static data (e.g. building typologies, census, and cadastre). By contrast, the decision support system which is being developed in the OPTIMUS project is based on the interlinking of five heterogeneous and dynamic data sources: weather, social behaviour, building performance, energy prices and energy production. These data sources are integrated using semantic technologies and then used to propose short-term action plans, which enable energy managers to optimize the building performance. For example, the DSS optimizes the boost time of the heating/cooling system taking into account the forecasting of the outdoor air temperature and the occupancy of the building. Accordingly, the DSS suggests selling/self-consuming of electricity produced by a PV system considering different scenarios of energy market and strategies (green, finance, intermediate, peak, load factor). Another example of a supported decision is the adjustment of the temperature set point, taking into consideration thermal comfort parameters (e.g., Predicted Mean Vote index) using occupants' inputs gathered with a mobile app.

The development process of the OPTIMUS DSS benefits from the experience and results obtained in the SEMANCO project, namely: 1. The tools used to create an ontology such as the editor Click-On, and 2. The SEMANCO ontology itself, which has been enhanced with the dynamic data required by the OPTIMUS project.

In OPTIMUS, the design of the DSS consists of four stages: 1. Defining the context, 2. Capturing the user requirements, 3. Identifying the dynamic data sources, and 4. Defining the application scenarios (Figure 1). Once the specifications have been defined, the DSS is developed consisting of the communication infrastructure (i.e. Semantic Framework), the DSS engine, and the DSS end-user interfaces.

The specification requirement process has been carried out in each of the three cities participating in the project: Sant Cugat del Vallès (Spain), Zaanstad (The Netherlands) and Savona (Italy).

Figure 1: Process of the development of the OPTIMUS DSS

Defining the context

The first phase consists of defining the context where the decision support system will be used. This involves highlighting the strengths, the vulnerabilities and the opportunities present considering the current energy strategies, environmental policies, municipal facilities and related infrastructures of the city in which the decision support system is going to be used. Typically, cities are evaluated in terms of energy efficiency, CO₂ emission intensity, and cost savings. An assessment framework –Smart City Energy Assessment Framework (SCEAF)– has been developed within the OPTIMUS project to estimate the energy efficient measures based on the suggestions of a decision support system or of an energy management strategy (Androulaki *et al.*, 2014). The SCEAF can be applied several times to evaluate the progression of city in a period of time.

Capturing the user requirements

The user requirements capture is carried out in iterations with the participation of end-users who will use the DSS. The information available from the city is collated and the functionalities of the DSS are derived from the inputs provided by the DSS users. The requirements are captured by means of surveys and mock-ups of the user interfaces, which are discussed with the end-users to verify with them the specified requirements and functionalities. The output of this phase is a report, which includes the main features of the public buildings and their building energy management systems.

Identifying dynamic data sources

This phase is dedicated to identifying the static and dynamic data sources that might be needed to meet the user requirements. In this stage of the process, it is necessary to audit the data sources to see if they can be integrated and used in the application scenarios (see the following section). The data items of the data sources are characterized by the following attributes: name, description, type of datum (e.g., string, integer, number, real, etc.), source (e.g., sensor, web platform, etc.), availability (e.g., public, private with license, etc.), owner (e.g., university, meteorological agency, etc.), unit of measure, accuracy, time step, spatial scale (e.g., group of buildings, building, etc.), and recording period length.

Defining the application scenarios

The last phase has to do with the definition of the scenarios where the DSS is going to be applied. A scenario describes the components that the DSS needs to suggest the end-user a short-term action to reduce energy consumption and to optimize the performance of buildings: input data, prediction models, intelligent rules, action plans and KPIs. The input data can be dynamic (e.g., energy consumption) and static (e.g., building partitions) which have been audited in the previous phase. The prediction models use dynamic data to forecast the performance of a building in the future. Black and grey box models –implemented with linear and non-linear methods– are used to create forecasts

based on the historical data. Intelligent rules use, both input and predicted data to find out possible short-term actions. An action plan is a set of actions suggested by the intelligent rules. Key performance indicators are used to evaluate the performance of the actions suggested by the DSS. These indicators are related to those used by the SCEAF to establish the baseline conditions in each pilot city.

The outputs of this phase are the specifications of a scenario encompassing the user requirements and the data sources previously identified. The mock-up previously developed during the capturing user requirements phase is included in the scenario specifications. Based on the specifications captured in the previous stages, the main components of the DSS are then developed.

Creating a semantic framework

The DSS relies on the interconnection of heterogeneous, dynamic data sources, which are used to suggest short-term action plans. Typically, these data are obtained from physical sensors installed in buildings, national agencies and web services. Moreover, the data comes from different realms (e.g. climate, energy costs) and have different characteristics (e.g. units of measure, aggregation level). A semantic framework is the communication infrastructure, which facilitates the transferring of data from the distributed sources, and the subsequent contextualization of the raw data in specific contexts. The development of the semantic framework encompasses: 1. The building of an ontology to model the different domains, and 2. The integration of dynamic data sources using a publish-and-subscribe system.

Ontology building process

An ontology is a formal shared conceptualization of one or various domains. In the OPTIMUS project, an ontology is the conceptualization of the energy performance of a building in operation. It embodies the terms and attributes to describe urban areas, neighbourhoods, buildings, building partitions, systems and metering devices, indicators such as energy consumption and CO₂ emissions, as well as climate and socio-economic factors.

A good practice in ontology design is to use terms based on norms and international standards and to reuse or expand existing ontologies. To build the OPTIMUS ontology we have relied on the urban energy ontology previously developed within SEMANCO project⁷. In this way, the conceptualization captured in the previous ontology could be re-used in the OPTIMUS project. This ontology captures the building and the technical system features such as building geometry, building thermal envelope, space cooling/heating systems, among others (Nemirovski *et al.*, 2013). To model real-time data sources, the Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) ontology has been chosen. The SSN ontology models sensors and observations. In particular, the ontology includes capabilities, measurement processes, observations and deployments in which sensors are used (Compton *et al.*, 2012). Since the SSN ontology provides only

⁷ <http://semanco-tools.eu/urban-energy-ontology>

core concepts, it needs to be extended with domain specific terms. The resulting OPTIMUS ontology is being coded in OWL using the Click-On editor. Currently, this ontology contains new 74 terms and new 33 relations and it borrows 1000 terms and relations from the existing Urban Energy and Semantic Sensor Network ontologies.

Semantic data integration

Semantic data integration is a process to transform and integrate raw data into information, which acquires meaning in specific use contexts using semantic technologies. A data integration process consists of four steps: 1. Data capturing modules, which retrieve the raw data from its source and transform them into RDF, 2. A publish-and-subscribe system (i.e., Ztreamey server), which receives data from modules and ensures the connectivity with the DSS, 3. A Semantic Service developed within the project to contextualize the data sent by the modules, and 4. A triple store (i.e., Openlink Virtuoso Server) to integrate the data.

The data integration process starts with the data capturing modules gathering raw data from the sources (e.g., sensor, web service). Those modules transform the raw data into RDF following the ontology structure. The data is sent to the DSS with the communication systems. The Semantic Service obtains the RDF data, which is enriched with the context (e.g., where was measured, which property is measuring, which units, etc.). Finally the Semantic Service stores the contextualized RDF data in a triple store.

Creating the DSS engine

At the core of the DSS engine lie the intelligent rules. These are a set of procedures to check if the input data match certain patterns to derive an action plan. The main goal of the DSS engine is to propose an action plan for the end user. To do so, the intelligent rules have to be fed with predicted, real-time and static data. To predict the building performance, a set of prediction models can be applied to determine an output variable by establishing the relationships between the output and input variables.

The process of building the DSS engine starts with the identification of intelligent rules requirements, in particular the data needs. Prediction models need to be developed for the data sources, which are to be forecasted. The prediction models need to be trained with a large amount of historical data. The proposed action plans include the calculation of key performance indicators, which will be used later for comparing with baseline or target scenarios. Examples of indicators are the reduction of the energy consumption, the reduction of the CO₂ emissions, cost reduction for energy needs, and an increase of RES in the final use. Currently, prediction models have been developed to forecast energy consumption of a building, indoor air temperature, energy prices, energy production of photovoltaic panels.

Developing the DSS end-user interfaces

The development of the end-user interfaces starts during the requirement capture phase while the first mock-ups are developed and discussed with the end-users. Later, several iterations are carried out for mock-ups to be discussed and refined. When a consensus is reached, the mock-up is implemented in the DSS. Finally, an evaluation with the end-users is carried out. Figure 2 shows two mock-ups from different iterations (left side of Figure 2) and their implementation in the DSS on the right side. The next step in the development of the system is to apply it in real conditions to optimize the building energy performance during the third year of the project. Further developments are expected following the results of the implementation.

Figure 2: Mock-ups (left side) and end-user interfaces (right side)

Conclusion

In the OPTIMUS project, we are developing a semantic-based Decision Support System, which is based on the methods and tools previously developed to create the SEMANCO platform. A first prototype of the DSS has been created based on the findings of requirements analysis conducted in three pilot cities. Requirement capturing is not a one-off process. It needs to be continuously validated with end-users and domain experts. One of the difficulties encountered in the development process has been obtaining generic application scenarios from the user requirements and the available data sources in each city since every building has a different infrastructure, data sources, regulations, cultural environments, occupancy profiles, uses, schedules, and targets. The OPTIMUS DSS represents an innovation with respect to the existing systems in so far as it is able to interlink five types of heterogeneous data sources (i.e., weather conditions, social behaviour, building energy performance, energy prices, and renewable energy production) in real time in order to suggest short-term action plans that enable public authorities to reduce energy consumption in public buildings.

A first prototype of the DSS has been developed including three action plans, four prediction models, and data integrated from five sources. The next step will be the application of the first prototype version in the three pilot cities, operating under real working conditions.

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